

FEATURES OF STANDARD LTE-R

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Annotatsiya. The tasks of ensuring the safety of train traffic, which are constantly increasing in complexity, especially in the passenger and freight sections of railways, the widespread introduction of information technologies in rail transport, which increase traffic volumes and reduce transport costs, determine the need to modernize morally and physically obsolete networks and systems in the industry technological radio communications, the further operation and maintenance of which are associated with more and more considerable expenses. In the conditions of continuous growth of requirements for radio communication services at limitation of resources (frequencies, radio means and etc.) the most perspective direction of modernization and radio communication development is creation and introduction of complex digital system of the radio communication integrating all kinds of a railway radio communication (train, station, repair-operative, general technology, data transfer, etc.) and providing operational compatibility of available radio networks of all services. An analysis of the capabilities of modern digital radio communication systems shows that their implementation, along with highly reliable radiotelephone (voice) communication, can provide a solution to many applied problems, including the organization of information transmission channels when creating a multi-level security system and train traffic control.

Digital radio communication systems are designed for operational control of the train movement by providing information exchange between the traffic control center and locomotives, as well as between locomotives of oncoming and following trains and other objects related to train work.

The introduction of LTE-R technology will allow infrastructure owners to reduce overall costs, reduce the total cost of network operation, expand their capabilities in the provision of various services and technologies, increase revenues by providing better data services. Therefore, studies aimed at introducing LTE-R technology are relevant.

Keywords: TRC, Bandwidth, LTE-R, EIRENE, SRC, GSM-R, RORC, ETCS, GSM-R.

The radio communication is the major element of a control system of rail transportation. It is applied at operative information interchange between the head of works and executors, and also executors with each other.

Principal views of networks of a technological railway radio communication are networks [1-8]:

A train radio communication (TRC);

Station radio communication (SRC);

A repair-operative radio communication (RORC).

TRC it is intended for an operational administration by movement of trains and allows to carry on office negotiations of the train dispatcher (DNC) and persons on duty on stations (DSP), and also other workers with machinists of train locomotives (TCHM), and also negotiations between machinists of passers and following going locomotives among themselves. Networks TRC will be organised basically under the linear scheme.

SPC it is intended for an operational administration by technological processes at station: for information interchange of heads of shunting and hilly works with machinists of shunting, hilly and economic locomotives, and also with other workers of stations connected with shunting work and processing of structures at stations.

POPC it is intended for an operative management of the workers occupied with the current maintenance of technical devices and carrying out of a damage control in divisions of track maintenances, an electrical supply, SCB(Signaling, centralisation and blocking) and communications.

Long Term Evolution (LTE) - the network of the fourth generation (4G) is characterized, available all Internet reports IP. In other words, the wireless industry takes the same way as in DSL, fibers and broadband IP on TV, paying attention of package switching instead of scheme switching. LTE offers strong mutual identification and additional continuous protection of confidentiality. Besides, it is commercial technology which does not demand any updating before it will be installed. In LTE there are many favourable qualities, such as:

A low waiting time;

Reduction of cost of transfer of unit given (1 bit);

Increase in a spectrum of services - more than new services for the smaller price;

Flexible use of existing and new frequency ranges;

The simplified architecture and open interfaces;
Comprehensible power consumption of user's devices.

Standard LTE-R represents possessing big flexibility the radio interface. The network type carries name E-UTRAN - Evolved Universal Terrestrial Radio Access Network (a developing universal land network of a radio access). In table 1 key parametres of technology LTE-R are resulted. The services given by networks LTE, have wider spectrum in comparison with networks 2G/3G.

Table 1

The Basic characteristics of system of a radio communication of standard LTE-R

Parametre	Features
Technology of plural access:	The direct channel (Downlink - DL) OFDMA The return channel (Uplink - UL) SC-FDMA.
Working range of frequencies:	450 MHz; 700 MHz; 800 MHz; 1800 MHz; 2, 1 GHz; 2, 4 - 2, 5 GHz; 2, 6 - 2, 7 GHz.
Bit speed:	Direct channel (DL) MIMO 2TX*2RX: 100 - 300 Mbit/sek; Return channel (UL): 50 - 172, 8 Mbit/sek.
Width of a strip of a radio channel	1, 4 - 20 MHz
Cell radius	5 - 30 км
Cell capacity (quantity of served subscribers)	More than 200 users at a strip of 5 MHz More than 400 users at a strip are more 5 MHz
Mobility: speed of rem	Until 250 km/h
Parametres of MIMO	Direct channel (DL): 2TX*2RX, 4TX*4RX Return channel (UL): 2TX*2RX
Value of a delay (latency)	5mc
Spectral efficiency	5 bit/sek/GHz
Supported types of modulation	Direct channel (DL): 64 QAM, QPSK, 16 QAM Return channel (UL): QPSK, 16 QAM
Duplex division of channels	FDD, TDD

First of all it is connected with high throughput of a network and the increased speed of data transmission, and also with transition to the concept «all through IP».

The basic services given by network LTE:

High sensitivity;

High throughput of a network;

High quality of service;

High speed of loading of the data;

High interactivity;

Voice transfer possibility on IP/IMS;

Completely IP e2e network;

There are more than channels of mobile TV;

Quality of the image of mobile TV is better;

Support online of games at the expense of low delays;

TDD, and FDD profiles;

Width of the channel to 20 MHz;

The improved antenna equipment.

Advantages of networks LTE-R

Noise immunity. LTE-R uses modulation OFDM for planning subcarrier for detection of a radio noise. It is the leader reference design a signal which quickly and precisely defines intervention by tracing of change of the channel on time and frequency areas. Besides, the simultaneous answer of several terminals with LTE-R helps to accelerate the answer to intervention. To avoid hindrances, LTE-R provides the high-grade mechanism for coding of repeated transfer, and IRC. This mechanism of planning of the microsecond level guarantees that network LTE-R distributes resources in the timely and dynamic way. Finding out a hindrance or cross communication, under a carrier with the highest relation C/I it will be defined. LTE-R Also gives AMC which will dynamically regulate modulation and a way of coding, it agree RSRP and SINR that will even more increase prevention of hindrances on network LTE-R. For control of hindrances in a network, LTE-R provides the high-grade independent mechanism. Besides, such algorithms as ICIC and CoMP improve possibility of network LTE-R for management of hindrances. Depending on used measures, LTE-R provides throughput for rendering of services with QoS, guarantees at detection of hindrances.

Powerful protection of safety. Safety of data transmission is important feature of networks LTE-R. Measures on confidentiality of identification of the user, check of authenticity of the subject, by the equipment of the user (UE) authentication,

confidentiality and integrity in signalling and the user data, access without a layer (NAS) safety are taken, etc.

Confidentiality of the identifier of the user. MME (object traffic control) allocates globally unique time identity to the user equipment which connects use EPS, for an exception of a frequent exchange to constants IMSI UE on radio-access.

Authentication object. Procedure authentication and coordination of keys is used for maintenance mutual authentication between the user and a network, and the agreement on a key of access for management of safety of object (KASME). KASME forms a basis for formation of a layer of access (Access Stratum) both enciphering NAS and integrity keys. Keys are used for radio-control over a resource in an access layer, and for a plane of the user and NAS alarm protection.

The user identification of the equipment. Check of authenticity of the equipment is initiated by means of MME through procedures EPS NAS. The inquiry about identification EMM goes to the user equipment with identification parameters (RAND, AUTN) and the Key Identifier of Set NAS (known as eKSI or KSIASME).

The user of the equipment answers MME with the authorised response, including the answer at successful data processing about authenticity checks. Then MME it is necessary to check up RES; intermediate KASME it is defined after successful end flowing EPS, co-ordinated between UE and MME.

Confidentiality and integrity for signalling and the user data. Protection of confidentiality and protection of integrity for signalling and the user data in EPS, is guaranteed by realisation of two levels of comparison of safety: AS and NAS.

AS safety. Enters into the complete set of the user equipment (for example, mobile phones) and small base stations LTE-R. Layer PDCP on the user equipment and at small base stations is responsible enciphering and integrity protection. Messages RRC are protected from integrity and ciphered, but the data of the user site only is ciphered [9-13].

NAS safety. Carried out messages NAS in the field of UE and MME. In this case communication of message NAS between UE and MME - the integrity protected and ciphered with additional heading of safety NAS. Enciphering of mechanisms can be used to provide signalling and the user confidentiality of the data between UE and EPS, while integrity and mechanisms can be used to provide signalling and the user integrity of the data.

Functionality. Support of various frequencies for LTE TDD (duplex transfer with division on time), FDD (duplex transfer with division on frequency) provides wider throughput;

Various variants of installation and simple procedure of preparation of platforms. Blocks of processing of base frequencies (BBU) can be installed as inside, and out of premises. External transmitters (RRU) are mounted on a column, on a mast or a concrete wall;

Power efficiency: loading decrease on environment at the expense of innovative amplifiers of capacity, devices of control of temperature, decrease in volumes of emissions and efficient control power consumption.

Increases quality of a covering of system and reduces expenses at the expense of installation RRU near to antenna system.

Comparison of standards GSM-R and LTE-R is presented in table 2.

Table 2

Comparison of standards GSM-R and LTE-R

The name of parametres	GSM-R	LTE-R
The European control system of movement of trains (ETKC)	Switching of channels of the data	Switching of packages of the data
PTP call	Switching of channels a vocal call	SIP on the basis of a vocal call
PTT call	Vocal services of a group call/service of a voice transfer	eMBMS groups LTE dialogue
Emergency Call	Vocal services of a group call	eMBMS groups LTE dialogue
Priority	eMLPP	QCI, ARP
Functional decisions	Point of management of service	Point of management of service
Arrangement - Dependent decisions	Point of management of service	Point of management of service
Access matrix	Point of management of service	Point of management of service

CONCLUSION

Equipping railways with digital radio networks is objectively necessary. The implementation of railway services over a wireless network is the main strategy in the

transition from analog radio communications to LTE-R. Railway wireless services can be classified into two categories: critical and general. Critical services are directly related to the movement of trains, for example, the transmission of voice calls by a dispatcher. General services have no relation to the movement of trains, but are necessary for passengers, the so-called client connection.

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